

Drug Utilization Pattern and Adverse Drug Reactions in Patients using Antidepressants

Jignesh Patel¹, Parth Trivedi²

^{1,2}Assistant Professor, Swaminarayan Institute of Medical Sciences & Research, Kalol, Gandhinagar

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Parth Trivedi

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Abstract:

Background: The most prevalent mental disorder in the world, depression is on the rise. Patients who stop their therapy or do not take their antidepressants as prescribed have poor treatment outcomes, a high relapse rate, and a bad quality of life.

Aims and Objectives: The purpose of the current study is to examine the drug use patterns seen in psychiatry department patients taking antidepressants as well as the adverse drug reactions (ADR) seen in these individuals.

Materials and Methods: The PSM hospital in psychiatry department was the site of the investigation. Data on demographics, diseases, and medications were gathered from 198 antidepressant prescriptions using a specifically created pro forma. Moreover, ADRs, if any, were recorded throughout their follow-up. Following a statistical analysis of the data, percentages and numbers were used to express the findings. Findings: 598 patients in all were examined. Of them, 42.13% were women and 57.86% were men. The age range between 41 and 60 was the most frequently afflicted and the one that received the highest dosage of antidepressants. The antidepressant that was prescribed the most was fluoxetine (48.32%). There were 957 prescriptions written overall, averaging 1.60 prescriptions per patient. In our analysis, generic versions of 75.65% of medications were prescribed.

Conclusions: Drug usage studies are necessary to promote the responsible and reasonable use of medications. Monitoring and analyzing adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and drug interactions related to antidepressant drug patterns is also becoming increasingly important. Antidepressant use in patients was determined to be appropriate in this investigation.

Keywords: Depression; Drug utilization study; Antidepressants.

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Introduction

These days, depression is a serious health problem that lowers a person's quality of life. Numerous medications have been developed to treat depression; however, the medications that are now being used may be overdosed or under dosed, which could result in unfavorable drug side effects or inadequate treatment, respectively. Hence, drug utilization studies (DUS) can be utilized to enhance the standard of care. DUS places a strong emphasis on the reasonability of drug use and offers helpful, evidence-based advice for deciding on policies at different health care levels.[1] These studies describe the pattern of drug use by estimating the number of patients exposed to drugs and the extent to which drugs are used in a particular area. Reasonable medication use in each patient implies suggests the economical prescription of a well-established medication at the ideal dosage for the appropriate indication. When medications are used inappropriately, patients are more likely to

experience adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and face financial hardship. Both wealthy and developing nations struggle with the issue of drug abuse, which poses a serious risk to medical practice.[2] Numerous DUS techniques have been applied both domestically and abroad, including those employed in qualitative research aimed at determining variations in application across national boundaries. Research on prescription pro forma focus on examining drug use patterns across patient demographics, including age, gender, and disease.[3] Facilitating rational medication use and developing measures to make the most efficient use of health resources are the ultimate goals of DUS. It is especially important in developing nations like India, where patients bear 72% of the cost of healthcare.[4] Additionally, due to irrational drug use, there is no way to properly report prescription errors that occur in hospitals. Medication is a vital component of human health maintenance. Arise

Interest in the study of drug prescribing trends has been piqued by the availability of newer medications and the growing awareness of their delayed harmful effects. A depressed mood, negative worry, loss of interest in routine activities, mental slowness and poor concentration, sleeplessness or increased sleep, significant weight loss or gain, psychomotor agitation or retardation, feelings of worthlessness and guilt, low energy, decreased libido, and suicidal thoughts that persist for at least two weeks are all indicative of depression. It interferes with a person's capacity to work, learn, sleep, eat, and engage in formerly enjoyable activities that result in significant personal burdens. Social and interpersonal functioning are significantly hampered by major depressive disorder.[5] Over the past few years, there has been a global shift in the prescribing pattern of antidepressants.[6] Recurrent episodes are common in patients with serious depression, necessitating long-term care for their condition. Since DUS are a low-cost method for assessing the prescribing patterns that are currently in place, these studies can offer changes that will lead to more logical and economical treatment procedures in the medical field. Thus, this study's objective is to evaluate the usage patterns of various antidepressant classes and ADR.

Materials and Methods

Data were gathered from research on outpatient prescriptions conducted at the BIMS, Belagavi, Department of Psychiatry. This study was a prospective observational one that ran from May 1st to September 30th of that year. Our study comprised 198 antidepressant-using participants in total.

The following criteria were needed to be met for inclusion in the study:

1. all outpatients, regardless of gender, receiving antidepressant medication and attending a psychiatric department between the ages of 18 and 60; and
2. All patients diagnosed with depression and any related illnesses who were prescribed antidepressant medication.

Criteria for Exclusion:

The study did not include

1. Inpatients from the psychiatry department or
2. Moms who were pregnant or nursing.

Method of Collection of Data

The data were collected prospectively by direct observation in a specially designed pro forma that contained pertinent details such as patient details, including registration number, age, gender, and diagnosis disease data, and drug data, after receiving approval and clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee.

Pro forma data on drug prescriptions, including brand-name or generic names, dosage, administration method, frequency, and adverse drug reactions, were gathered. The prescription medications were categorized using the daily dosage (DDD) classification system established by the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC).

In our investigation, antidepressant prescriptions were written for numerous doses, and the average of those daily doses was taken as the prescribed daily dosage (PDD). The PDD-to-DDD ratio was then computed.

Statistical Application

The data collected were analyzed statistically using descriptive statistics, namely mean and standard deviation for quantitative variables and nonparametric tests for qualitative variables. The analysis was performed using Chi-square test, and the results were expressed as numbers and percentage. Significant values- p value of <0.05.

Results

Based on the psychiatric department's inclusion criteria, a total of 598 cases were chosen and examined. In patients with depressive illness, fluoxetine (50.27%) was the most often prescribed antidepressant medication, followed by sertraline (40.29%), amitriptyline (25.31%), and escitalopram (3.43%).

Age in years

The age group of 41–60 years old was the most frequently afflicted and the one that received the highest dosage of antidepressants.

Figure 1: Prevalence of psychiatric disorders and use of antidepressants

Table 1: Prevalences of Psychiatry disorders based on sex status

Indication	Number of patients (%)		Total number of patients (%)	Chi-square	P-value
	Male	Female			
Depressive disorder	320 (57.86)	233 (42.13)	553 (92.47)	13.68	*P<0.01
Schizophrenia with depression	17 (48.57)	18 (51.42)	35 (1.5)	0.02	P>0.05
BPAD	5 (55.55)	4 (44.44)	9 (5.85)	0.12	P>0.05

Sex-wise Distribution

Males made up the majority of patients using antidepressants for depressive disorders, which is representative of the community at risk.

Depressive disorder (92.47%), schizophrenia with depression (7.18%), and bipolar affective disorder (BPAD) (0.5%) were the most common diagnoses

among the patients taking antidepressants. Figure 2 illustrates depression illness, which was the most prevalent psychiatric diagnosis among these.

Marital Status

Table 2 displays the percentage of married individuals with depressive illness in our study, followed by singles and divorcees.

Table 2: Prevalences of Psychiatry disorders based on marital status

Diagnosis	Married (%)	Unmarried (%)	Divorcee (%)	Chi-square	P-value
Depressive disorder (554)	175 (88.58)	81 (14.62)	15 (3.61)	498.11	*P<0.001
Schizophrenia with depression (35)	15 (7.57)	4 (11.42)	3 (8.57)	32.33	*P<0.01
BPAD (9)	8 (88.8)	1 (11.11)	0 (0)	3.44	*P<0.05

Occupational Status

The highest rate of patients suffering from depressive disorder was employees followed by housewives, unemployees, students, laborers, and farmers.

Educational Status: In our study, the highest rate of depression was seen in patients with secondary education followed by primary education, patients with no education, and those with tertiary education and is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Prevalences of Psychiatry disorders based on educational status

Drug name	Primary (%)	Secondary (%)	Tertiary (%)	No education	Chi-square	P-value
Depressive disorder (554)	79 (39.76)	90 (45.02)	29 (5.23)	21 (3.79)	371.49	P<0.001
Schizophrenia with depression (35)	15 (7.85)	14 (7)	1 (2.85)	5 (14.28)	16.09	P<0.01
BPAD (9)	4 (2.44)	5 (2.52)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0	P>0.05

Concomitant Medications

Table 4 lists the patients in our study who were taking anxiolytics (25.58%), antipsychotics (5.51%), antihypertensive medications (0.56%), antidiabetic medications (0.99%), and anti-Parkinsonism medication (0.33%) concurrently with antidepressants. The average daily dosage of antidepressants in our research.

Number of Drugs per Prescription

In our study, majority of the patients received antidepressants as monotherapy (49.16%).

ATC-DDD Classification

All antidepressant drugs were coded by ATC classification.

In our study, for each prescription, there were mul-

multiple doses of the antidepressants prescribed, and the average of the daily doses of antidepressant was taken as PDD. And then, PDD-to-DDD ratio was calculated and is depicted.

ADR

Patients who came to the psychiatric outpatient clinic were asked to come back once every fifteen days for a fresh prescription and to inquire about

ADR. The most common side effects of amitriptyline therapy were weight gain (0.83%), dry mouth (0.83%), and nausea (0.83%). Weight gain (1.67%) and nausea (1.5%) were more common side effects of fluoxetine therapy. Gastritis (1.33%), sleeplessness (0.83%), nausea (2.17%), and weight gain (2.0%) were the most frequent side effects reported with sertraline. Escitalopram was related to insomnia (0.66%).

Table 4: Concomitant drugs along with antidepressants

Concomitant medications	
Category of drugs	Number of patients (%)
Anxiolytics	
Clonazepam	164 (27.42)
Alprazolam	2 (0.33)
Diazepam	1 (0.16)
Antipsychotics	
Risperidone	17 (2.84)
Olanzapine	22 (3.67)
Antihypertensive drugs	
Amlodipine	2 (0.33)
Atenolol	2 (0.33)
Antidiabetic drugs	
Metformin	3 (0.50)
Glimipiride	2 (0.33)
Voglibose	1 (0.16)
Anti-Parkinsonism drugs	
Trihexyphenidyl	2 (0.33)

Table 5: Mean daily dose of antidepressants

Antidepressants	Number of prescriptions	Mean dose
Amitriptyline		
25 mg	147	25±0
Fluoxetine		
20 mg 40 mg	119	20.13±1.66
Sertraline		
50 mg 100 mg	179	30.45±10.34
Escitalopram		
10 mg	15	10±0

Discussion

A person's personal and overall health can be adversely affected by depression, a significant medical condition. Depression mostly results from a confluence of environmental, psychological, and genetic variables. Furthermore, a few risk variables include a family history of depression, alterations in lifestyle, substance misuse, persistent medical disorders, and pharmaceutical use. These risk factors may improve slightly or remain unchanged following antidepressant medication treatment.

A total of 198 cases were chosen and examined for our study based on the psychiatric department's inclusion criteria. A total of 457 prescription medications were issued. The most often prescribed antidepressant medication among patients was fluoxetine (48.32%), which was followed by

escitalopram (3.17), amitriptyline (26.42%), sertraline (47.82%), and fluoxetine (48.32%). Individuals between the ages of 41 and 60, who make up 59.30% of all patients, were the most often affected and used the greatest number of antidepressants. Males (57.86%) made up the majority of patients using antidepressants for depressive illness in our study, compared to females (42.13%), BPAD (1.5%), schizophrenia with depression (6.18%), and depressive disorder (92.47%) were the most common diagnoses among the individual's taking antidepressants. In our study, the majority of patients who received antidepressants were married (81.58%) and housewives (30.86%), followed by single people (14.62%) and divorcees (3.05%). Based on their occupational status for depressive disorder, employees had the highest rate of patients receiving

antidepressants (43.86%), while farmers had the lowest rate (1.26%).

Patients with secondary and post-secondary education had the highest rate of depression, while patients with no education and those with pre-secondary education had the lowest rates of depression. The most common medications taken in addition to antidepressants include anxiolytics, antipsychotics, antihypertensive drugs, antidiabetic drugs, and anti-Parkinsonism drugs. In our study, antidepressant monotherapy was administered to the majority of patients (49.16%).

A total of 198 cases were chosen and examined for our study based on the psychiatric department's inclusion criteria. A total of 457 prescription medications were issued. The most common antidepressant medication prescribed to patients was fluoxetine (48.32%), which was followed by sertraline (47.82%), amitriptyline (26.42%), and escitalopram (3.17). These findings contrast with those of another study, which found that escitalopram was the most commonly prescribed antidepressant medication [7] and that selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) were the most commonly used medication for depression.[8] SSRIs and SNRIs are currently the medications of choice for the majority of psychiatrists treating depression, and they unquestionably play a role in the treatment of depression. It is quite beneficial to combine SSRIs with tricyclic antidepressants were the most frequently impacted, making up 59.30% of all patients, and they used the highest number of antidepressants. One of the factors influencing mental health status is age because aging makes a person more susceptible to environmental cues, which may account for some of the findings in our study. Our results, however, conflict with research by Ghosh and Chaudhury [10] which found that 51.96% of antidepressant-using patients were in the 18–30 age range. Compared to children or adults, adolescents have a higher incidence of depression; the likelihood of developing depression rises from 5% in early adolescence to as high as 20% by the conclusion of this stage [11]. In contrast, the rising prevalence of depression in is caused by a prodrome of dementia or, more frequently in later life, a psychological or biological reaction to events like physical disease and caring.[12] Antidepressant use was shown to be higher in people over 60 in a different study.[13]

Males (57.86%) made up the majority of patients receiving antidepressants for depressive disorder in our study, compared to females (42.13%). This difference may be explained by the fact that men are more likely than females to experience stress at work. Our results, which indicate that the proportion of female and male patients was 51.50% and 48.50%, respectively, differ from those of the study.[14] It seems that women are more likely

than males to experience depression at even lower stress levels, and they also exhibit heightened neuroendocrine reactions to stress. [15,16] Furthermore, compared to male patients, female patients are more likely to disclose their symptoms of depression, which could account for the gender disparity in illness prevalence [17]

In our study, depressive disorder (92.47%), schizophrenia with depression (6.18%), and BPAD (1.5%) were the most common disorders among the patients taking antidepressants. The most prevalent psychiatric condition among them was depressive disorder. The most prevalent mental ailment, depression, is on the rise everywhere in the world. Our study's results are in line with another study's, which indicates that depression (36.33%) and anxiety (27.5%) and schizophrenia (17%) were the most prevalent disorders among patients visiting the psychiatric OPD.[18] Numerous psychosocial factors have been linked to depression, including perceived poor health, low levels of spirituality, loneliness, dependency, inadequate family care and affection, insufficient time spent with children, stressful life events, and low levels of family or social support.

The bulk of patients in our study who were prescribed antidepressants were married (81.58%) and housewives (30.86%), followed by single people (14.62%) and divorcees (4.05%). Our results may be explained by the ongoing stress that comes with being married, which raises the risk of depression. Our results are in line with research by Dutta et al. [20] that revealed married patients (76%) and housewives (45.14%) made up the bulk of patients who received antidepressants. According to a different survey, the distribution of patients taking psychiatric medications was nearly equal between married patients (36.4%) and single patients (38.6%).[21] In their research, Patten et al. [22] discovered substantial relationships between sex, age, and marital status, with single women reporting decreased incidence of depression as they grew older and remained single Males are reporting higher depression rates. Based on the occupational status for depressive disorder, employees had the highest rate of patients receiving antidepressants (43.86%), while farmers had the lowest rate (1.26%). This could be because of a variety of factors, including time pressure, income, physical activity level, job security, demands, and job dissatisfaction, which can all lead to a person losing confidence and developing depression. Our findings contradict those of another study, which indicated that among male-dominated occupational categories, machine operators, laborers, farmers, and unskilled manual workers had higher rates of depression.[23]

International research revealed that whereas farmers in Norway and the UK had greater levels

of depression than comparison groups, farmers in France and Canada had lower levels of depression.[24] Additional research revealed a substantial correlation between a spouse's weekly work hours and the likelihood of an individual experiencing depressive symptoms and thoughts of suicide. This suggests that extended work hours have an impact not only on the mental well-being of the individual but also on their partners.[25]

Pre-secondary schooling and patients without any education had the lowest risk of depression, whereas secondary and post-secondary schooling had the highest rate. When education fails to provide fulfilling employment, overeducated people experience depression. Other problems include intense job rivalry, difficulty applying skills at work, and the possibility of working more hours for less money. Depression may result from any of these circumstances. Our study's results are in line with those of another study, which found that respondents with less education than a secondary school had the lowest lifetime depression rate (9.1%), while respondents with other post-secondary education had the highest lifetime depression rate (13.4%).[26]

The following medications were found to be the most frequently taken concurrently with antidepressants in our study: anxiolytics, antipsychotics, antihypertensive medications, antidiabetic medications, and medications for Parkinson's disease. Antidepressant dose equivalency is crucial for both clinical practice and research.[27] Amitriptyline, fluoxetine, sertraline, and escitalopram had mean daily doses of 25 ± 0 , 20.13 ± 1.66 , 30.45 ± 10.34 , and 10 ± 0 in our study. Mohanta et al. conducted a study, [28] Sertraline's mean daily dose was 52.63 and fluoxetine's mean was 26.50. Antidepressant monotherapy was administered to the majority of individuals in our study (49.16%). Rush et al.'s study [29], which evaluated the effects of monotherapy and combined therapy on depression outcomes, found no statistically significant differences between the results of patients receiving a single antidepressant and those receiving a combination of antidepressants. The incidence and severity of side effects have grown as a result of antidepressant polypharmacy, according to a study by Tianmei et al. [30]. In our analysis, the ATC classification was used to code all antidepressant medications. The World Health Organization established the current classification system for medications in 1976. (31)

A stands for the anatomical site of action, T for the therapeutic indication, and C for the drug's chemical class in the ATC classification.[32] The daily assumed maintenance dose (DDD) of a medication used for its primary indication in adults is calculated.[33] DDD is utilized in

pharmacoepidemiology research where it is assumed that one DDD is consumed daily in order to compare costs,[34] assess compliance, and determine illness prevalence.[35] Data on drug use expressed in DDDs are typically presented in units that account for variations in population size. This estimate is helpful for medications that are taken on a long-term basis, like antipsychotics and antidepressants, among many others.[36] The PDD is the typical daily dosage of a medication that is in fact advised.[33]

When sertraline and amitriptyline were combined, a ratio of less than one was seen, which suggested under dosing. For fluoxetine, a ratio greater than one was seen, signifying overdose; in contrast, escitalopram and other antidepressants displayed a PDD-to-DDD ratio of one, indicating appropriate dosing. All antidepressants showed adequate dose in research by Lahon et al. [37], with the exception of duloxetine and mirtazapine, which frequently showed under dosing.

Long-term patients were required to follow up with the outpatient psychiatric department once every fifteen days, during which time the reported adverse drug reactions were documented. ADRs related to amitriptyline therapy included weight gain, dry mouth, and nausea. Weight gain and nausea were more likely when taking fluoxetine. Gastritis, sleeplessness, nausea, and weight gain were among the more frequent side effects of sertraline. The use of escitalopram was linked to insomnia, which runs counter to research by Mukherjee et al.[38] where the most frequent adverse drug reactions (ADRs) were dry mouth, nausea, and tremor; in another study, the most common ADRs linked to antidepressant usage were agitation, anxiety, and insomnia.[39] In our study, no fixed dose combinations were used, and 75.65% of the medications were prescribed using their generic names. 46.81% of prescribed medications came from the WHO model list of essential medications, and every medication was filled in the hospital pharmacy. Neither a history of suicidal thoughts nor any instances of antidepressant switching during therapy were observed in the patients.

A bigger sample size would have allowed for more accurate results from our investigation. A longer period of follow-up for these individuals would have yielded more data regarding the effectiveness and safety of the antidepressants that were administered.

Conclusion

DUS has gained popularity as a technique for health system evaluation in recent years. Of the major mental illnesses, depression has shown to be the most difficult to treat. Major depressive disorder and other mental health issues were treated

with antidepressants. DUS must promote the responsible and reasonable use of pharmaceuticals. The medical staff should be concerned about tracking and evaluating adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and any medication interactions with prescribed antidepressants. Most of the prescriptions in our study were written in accordance with accepted practices. Antidepressants were determined to be appropriate for these patients, and the majority of the medications were prescribed under generic names. The DU study data that will be examined will be of tremendous benefit to physicians in terms of confirming data on safer and better drug use as well as lowering adverse drug reaction rates. We were unable to confirm if the prescribed prescriptions were actually taken, which is why more research with appropriate monitoring and long-term follow-up is necessary. Depression is a chronic problem, and in order for the illness to go away, one must continue taking meds.

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